

1 **Diagnosing the traffic impact on roadside soils through a multianalytical data analysis of the**
2 **concentration profiles of traffic-related elements**

3
4 3
5
6 4 Jose Antonio Carrero*, Iker Arrizabalaga, Julen Bustamante, Naiara Goienaga, Gorka Arana, Juan
7
8 5 Manuel Madariaga

9
10 6
11
12 7 Department of Analytical Chemistry, University of the Basque Country (UPV/EHU), P.O. Box 644,
13
14 8 E-48080 Bilbao, Spain.

15
16 9 Tel +34 946015551 e-mail: joseantonio.carrero@ehu.es
17

18 10

19
20 11

21
22 12 **Abstract**

23
24 13 The road traffic has become one of the most serious environmental problems in many cities and the
25
26 14 main source of pollution of urban soils. To diagnose properly the magnitude of such impacts on
27
28 15 roadside soils, eight urban and metropolitan soils were selected as a function of traffic density,
29
30 16 distance to the road and years of operation, for which the concentration of 60 elements (major, minor
31
32 17 and trace elements) were measured by semi-quantitative ICP-MS after acid digestion, as a first step in
33
34 18 assessing the traffic impact. With this information, a comprehensive study was carried out focusing on
35
36 19 the quantitative analysis of the concentration of 46 elements from the 8 sampling areas, analysing the
37
38 20 vertical and horizontal distribution of the metals in the roadside soils. The chemometric analysis
39
40 21 showed that only the traffic-related elements accumulate in topsoil and present a high decreasing
41
42 22 profile with depth and the distance to the road; however, this clear behaviour takes places only in old
43
44 23 roads that have undergone the traffic impact for a long time, but not in new roads or roads with low
45
46 24 traffic density. Finally, the geoaccumulation indexes are suggested to be used instead of the local
47
48 25 guidelines to assess the pollution state of the roadside soils, especially for the emerging trace
49
50 26 elements like Antimony.

51
52
53 27

54
55 28 **Keywords**

56
57 29 Roadside soil, ICP-MS, Traffic impact, Traffic-related elements, PCA
58

59
60 30
61
62
63
64
65

31 1. Introduction

32
33 With the rapid development of road communication networks in the last century, the road traffic has
34 become one of the most serious environmental problems in many cities and the main source of
35 pollution of urban soils. Moreover, the contribution of road traffic to global emissions of atmospheric
36 pollutants is increasing every year (Amato et al., 2011; Hjortenkrans et al., 2007). The dispersion of
37 these contaminants is determined by weather conditions and can be deposited in surrounding areas
38 such as urban and agricultural soils as well as waters. Among all the possible pollutants coming from
39 the road traffic, metals and polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (PAHs) are the most dangerous
40 (Aatmeeyata and Sharma, 2011; Amato et al., 2011; Lough et al., 2005). Whereas organic compounds
41 can be transformed or degraded by means of the microbial action of the soil in others innocuous
42 compounds such as water and CO₂ (Wu et al., 2008) metals can remain in the media for a long time
43 since they do not undergo decay (Chen et al., 2010).

44
45 Roadside soils have become an important sampling point to assess the anthropogenic concentrations
46 of metals. Several studies have been carried out since years ago by different authors showing the
47 pollution of roadside soils due to the traffic and it has been observed that the roadside soils have a
48 high content of metals (Apegyei et al., 2011; Bretzel and Calderisi, 2006; Chen et al., 2010; Wei and
49 Yang, 2010). Most of them have focused on well-known traffic pollutants as Pb, Cd, or Zn (Garcia and
50 Millán, 1998; Gratani et al., 1992; Lagerwerff and Specht, 1970; Viard et al., 2004). Other authors
51 have extended the study to the analysis of metals in plants and urban trees (Li et al., 2007; Massadeh
52 et al., 2009; Olowoyo et al., 2010) or to airborne particulate matter (Oliva and Espinosa, 2007).

53
54 The road traffic involves several potential sources of metals, such as exhaust fumes, tire and brake
55 wear, oil spill, road pavement, building materials for traffic safety or resuspension of soil and road dust
56 (McKenzie et al., 2009; Thorpe and Harrison, 2008; Wei and Yang, 2010). It has been observed that
57 the roadside soils have a high content of metals, especially Pb, Ba, Zn, Cd and Cu. A study carried out
58 in Sweden indicates that diffuse pollution generated by road traffic is the main source for the 90% of
59 Cd, 40% of Cu and more than 99% of both Cr and Ni, 85% of Pb and 80% of Zn found in the roadside
60 (Bergbaeck et al., 2001).

61

62 Before banning the use of leaded petrol, lead was discharged as organic or particulate lead in the
63 exhaust fumes. Although there has been a significant reduction in the lead emissions from vehicles
64 since it was banned in Europe (Directive, 1998) and other countries worldwide around 1998-2002, a
65 major reservoir of lead in roadside soils still remains (MacKinnon et al., 2011). Besides lead, other
66 metals such as Cd, Cr, Cu, Ni and V are also issued in the combustion of fossil fuels, such as petrol
67 (de Miguel et al., 1997). Zinc is used in the process of vulcanization of tires as zinc oxide (Adachi and
68 Tainosho, 2004), and as antioxidant in the engine oil. As a result of the tire wear and/or leaks of
69 engine oil and emission of the exhaust fumes, zinc is deposited on the roadside soils (Councell et al.,
70 2004). In addition, the tires have trace amounts of other metals such as Cd, Co, Cr, Cu, Hg, Mn, Mo,
71 W, Ni and Pb (Apeageyi et al., 2011; Hjortenkrans et al., 2007). Other authors associate it to the
72 emission of other metals such as, Sn, Cd, Cr, Ni, Pb, Zn, Zr and Mo (Apeageyi et al., 2011; Dongarra
73 et al., 2009; Hjortenkrans et al., 2007; Johansson et al., 2009) in smaller amounts. Chromium is
74 mainly derived from the erosion or abrasion processes, including metal plating and bodywork.

75

76 Traffic pollutants could show a different vertical and horizontal distribution pattern depending on their
77 own nature, their main form of diffusion or their primary source. There is a general agreement that
78 these metals decrease in concentration with depth and with distance from the roadway (Liu et al.,
79 2009). Polluted roadside soils may pose a risk to health if the metals are transferred to other
80 reservoirs. Some studies have demonstrated that Cu, Pb and Zn show a significant anthropic
81 enrichment and can be transported into rivers, lakes, near shore seawater or sediment (Meland et al.,
82 2010; Sutherland et al., 2000). On the soil, these pollutants can be transported to the aerial parts of
83 vegetation, bioaccumulating in them (Veschambre et al., 2003; Wiseman et al., 2013). Therefore,
84 humans and animals can ingest metals directly through inhalation of soil dust (Amato et al., 2011) or
85 the metals can enter the food chain as a result of the ingestion of edible plants (Wei and Yang, 2010).

86

87 Soil is considered polluted when chemicals are present or other alterations have been made to its
88 natural environment. In this sense, traffic emissions involve an anthropogenic input of metals to
89 surrounding soils, altering their natural composition. There are different methods to estimate the
90 metallic pollution level of an altered soil. The geoaccumulation index, I_{geo} , is a simple method for

91 assessing soil quality, providing a simple way of comparing the extent of metal pollution of the urban
1 92 soils. It has been used since the late 1960s, and has been widely employed in European trace metal
2 93 studies. Originally used for bottom sediments (Müller, 1969), it has been successfully applied to the
3 94 measurement of soil pollution (Li et al., 2011). The I_{geo} enables the assessment of pollution by
4 95 comparing current and background concentrations, although it is not always easy to reach background
5 96 soil layers. It is calculated using the following equation: $I_{geo} = \log_2(C_n/1.5*B_n)$, where, C_n is the measured
6 97 concentration of the element in soil and B_n is the geochemical background value. The constant 1.5
7 98 allows us to analyze natural fluctuations in the content of a given element in the environment and to
8 99 detect very small anthropogenic influences. According to the geoaccumulation index, soils can be
9 100 classified as non-polluted ($I_{geo} < 1$), very slightly polluted ($1 < I_{geo} < 2$), slightly polluted ($2 < I_{geo} < 3$),
10 101 moderately polluted ($3 < I_{geo} < 4$), highly polluted ($4 < I_{geo} < 5$) and very highly polluted ($I_{geo} > 5$).
11 102 However, metal background values are not enough to establish soil deterioration state and other
12 103 methods are used as reference values within environmental protection policy framework to assess the
13 104 risk for the ecosystems. This is the case of the Basque Indicative Values for Assessment (VIEs)
14 105 (IHOBE, 1998), which are scientifically based on a generic assessment criterion to help evaluate long-
15 106 term risks to human health and to the ecosystem due to chemical pollution in soils from the Basque
16 107 Country (North of Spain).

108
109 The established methods to diagnose the traffic impact on roadside soils may not be the most
110 adequate due to the possible simultaneous presence of several sources of pollution. The aim of this
111 study was to identify the current traffic-related elements (TREs) and to establish its concentration
112 profiles in both, horizontal and vertical distribution, in order to monitor the contribution of traffic to
113 environmental pollution and risk and to assess their level of pollution. To attain those objectives,
114 selected soils with different levels of impacts (proximity to the roads and time exposed to traffic) were
115 screened, in a first step, by semiquantitative ICP-MS analysis (Laborda et al., 2001) to search for all
116 constituents of significance. In a second step, only those elements with a significant concentration
117 were quantitatively determined as a function of the horizontal profile and vertical depth. Finally,
118 chemometric analysis of the data, as well as, the mentioned methods for assessing the quality of soils
119 were applied to decide the most simple and relevant method to diagnose properly the impact of traffic-
120 related elements.

121

1
2 **122 2. Material and methods**

3
4 123

5
6 **124 2.1. Sampling design**

7
8 125

9
10 126 Four different sampling areas were selected according to their different exposure times to traffic
11
12 127 impact. The first study area is an old secondary road located in the Mungia-Bilbao road
13
14 128 (43°19'35.53''N, 2°52'20.39''W, Biscay, north of Spain), near the city of Bilbao, that has been in
15
16 129 service for more than 60 years and exposed to high traffic impact for a long time till the construction of
17
18 130 a new highway two decades ago. Even today this secondary road suffers a medium traffic density
19
20 131 about 1800 vehicles per day and 5.9% of them are of high tonnage (BFA/DFB, 2004). The second
21
22 132 study area is a modern highway with more than 20 years of service, designed in parallel to the old
23
24 133 road but separated by a stream that ensures the non translation of anthropic elements by runoff from
25
26 134 one soil to the other; it bears most of the traffic in the area and has a traffic density of about 28.200
27
28 135 vehicles per day from the year 2004 until now, being 5.7% of them of high tonnage (BFA/DFB, 2004).

29
30 136

31
32 137 The other two locations are two roundabouts in Berango (43°21'46''N 3°00'12''O) and Sopelana
33
34 138 (43°22'45''N 2°59'56''O), both in the metropolitan Bilbao. In Berango the roundabout was built 5
35
36 139 years ago, whereas the one from Sopelana was only one year old when the sampling was done and
37
38 140 therefore it had scarcely been exposed to traffic impact. The Fig. S1 shows a picture of the above
39
40 141 described sampling zones together with a map locating the metropolitan area of Bilbao, in the north of
41
42 142 Spain.

43
44 143

45
46 144 In a first stage, a preliminary study was conducted collecting roadside soil samples from the upper 0-
47
48 145 10 cm at different sampling points in the secondary road and the highway. Sampling in the highway
49
50 146 was carried out at a distance of 0.5, 3, 6 and 9 m from the highway (H 0.5, H 3, H 6 and H 9 sample
51
52 147 codes). In the secondary road, soil samples were collected at both roadsides (SR L and SR R sample
53
54 148 codes) but the sampling was only completed at 0.5 m in the west roadside and at 3 m in the east
55
56 149 roadside because of the existence of a road cut and a stream that precluded sampling at a greater
57
58 150 distance. Control soils were sampled 700 m away from both traffic roads in the north-west direction. In

59
60
61
62
63
64
65

151 a second stage, and in order to study the vertical and horizontal distribution of metals, soil sample
152 transects of 20 cm in depth were also collected at different distances from the highway at 0 meters
153 (S0m) just immediately after the road, and at 1 and 3 meters of distance (S1m and S3m). In this area
154 there is no channel and thus, runoff waters from the road arrive directly to the soil. Samples were
155 divided in subsamples of 2-3 cm of depth (S1m A - S1m H and S3m A - S3m F). The same procedure
156 was carried out in roundabouts from Berango and Sopelana, where sampling was done at 0 m and 1
157 m of distance to the road (BE 0A – BE 0D, BE 1A – BE 1D, SO 0A – SO 0E and SO 1A – SO 1D).
158 Samples were mainly clay soils, as this is the typical soil composition of the Bilbao metropolitan area.

2.2. Analytical procedure

161
162 All plastic and glassware material in contact with samples or ICP-MS solutions were soaked in a 10%
163 HNO₃ bath for at least 24 h, then rinsed twice with Elix (Millipore, USA) quality water and finally rinsed
164 with Milli-Q water (18.2 MΩ cm, Millipore, USA). After drying the material in a laminar airflow hood
165 inside a class 100 clean room, it was stored in clean plastic bags until use. Nitric acid (69%) and
166 hydrochloric acid (36%) used for microwave digestion and ICP-MS analysis were of Tracepur grade
167 and supplied by Merck (Darmstadt, Germany).

168
169 Soil samples were air dried in a fume hood during 24 h, ground in a planetary ball mill Pulverisette 6
170 (Fritsch, Germany) for their homogenization and sieved to particle size under 2 mm removing small
171 stones and vegetation remains. Acid digestion of the soils was conducted according to the
172 US Environmental Pollution Agency (USEPA) 3051A method (EPA, 2007) in a microwave oven
173 Multiwave 3000 (Anton Paar, Graz, Austria) equipped with a rotor 8XF100 with PTFE vessels of 100
174 mL. 0.5 g of samples were accurately weighed in each Teflon vessel, 9 mL of nitric acid and 3 mL of
175 hydrochloric acid were added and allowed to react for a few seconds before closing the vessels. The
176 extracts were filtered with 0.45 μm pore size filters (Millipore Millex-HV) and were kept in the
177 refrigerator until their analysis.

178
179 Elemental analysis was carried out using a Perkin Elmer SCIEX 9000 ICP-MS (Toronto, Canada)
180 inside a class 100 clean room. Sample solutions were diluted to 1% HNO₃ concentration prior to

181 analysis. The performance of an ICP-MS instrument strongly depends on the operating conditions and
182 therefore, the plasma operating conditions such as the nebulizer flow rate, the position of the torch
183 and the ion lens voltages of the instrument were optimized everyday prior to any experiment with a
184 10 ng/mL standard solution of Mg, Rh, In, Ba, Pb and U. The nebulizer gas-flow rate was optimized to
185 obtain a good compromise between high sensitivity and low oxide levels (lower than 3% for CeO/Ce).
186 Two different methods were used for data acquisition, a semi-quantitative one for the first preliminary
187 study and a quantitative one for the subsequent analyses. Sample acquisition and experimental
188 conditions for the semi-quantitative method are published in a previous work (Carrero et al., 2010).
189 Experimental conditions for the quantitative analysis are summarised in Table S1.

190
191 In a first approach, soil samples from the secondary road and the highway were screened for 60
192 elements by means of multi-element semiquantitative analysis using the Perkin Elmer TotalQuant III
193 software (Laborda et al., 2001; Soldevila et al., 1998). Common isobaric interferences are pre-
194 programmed and corrections are automatically applied. The software has stored pre-calibrated
195 intensities per concentration unit covering the required m/z range. In order to increase the accuracy,
196 these values are updated by running samples spiked with a few selected elements with known
197 concentration (Ag, Al, As, Cd, Co, Cr, Cu, Fe, Hg, Mg, Mn, Ni, Pb, Sb, Se, Sn, V and Zn at 20 ng/g)
198 and using Rhenium (Re) as internal standard. The aim of this multi-elemental semi-quantitative
199 analysis was to obtain a first list of the traffic-related elements at the same time that the study area is
200 limited to those sites more impacted by the traffic impact.

201
202 After the screening of the soils, a quantitative method using external calibration was applied in order to
203 conduct vertical and horizontal metal distribution analysis. In addition to the secondary road and the
204 highway, soil samples from the roundabouts from Berango and Sopelana were also included in this
205 study. 46 metals, including alkaline, transition metals and rare earth elements (REE) were determined
206 in the samples of the different sampling areas measuring the following isotopes: ^7Li , ^{23}Na , ^{24}Mg , ^{27}Al ,
207 ^{39}K , ^{43}Ca , ^{47}Ti , ^{51}V , ^{53}Cr , ^{55}Mn , ^{57}Fe , ^{59}Co , ^{60}Ni , ^{63}Cu , ^{68}Zn , ^{75}As , ^{82}Se , ^{88}Sr , ^{93}Nb , ^{98}Mo , ^{107}Ag , ^{114}Cd ,
208 ^{120}Sn , ^{123}Sb , ^{138}Ba , ^{184}W , ^{202}Hg , ^{205}Tl , ^{89}Y , ^{208}Pb , ^{139}La , ^{140}Ce , ^{141}Pr , ^{142}Nd , ^{152}Sm , ^{153}Eu , ^{158}Gd , ^{159}Tb ,
209 ^{164}Dy , ^{165}Ho , ^{166}Er , ^{169}Tm , ^{174}Yb , ^{175}Lu , ^{232}Th , ^{238}U . ^{45}Sc , ^{74}Ge , ^{115}In , ^{187}Re and ^{209}Bi were used as
210 internal standards. All solutions were prepared using Milli-Q water. ICP-MS standard solutions were

211 prepared from Alfa Aesar (Specpure®, Plasma standard solution, Germany) stock solutions. For
212 quality assurance purposes soil certified reference materials (SRM 2711, total content; and BCR
213 142R, *aqua regia* soluble content) and a freshwater containing trace elements (SRM 1640) were
214 routinely analyzed in each sample batch.

2.3. Physicochemical properties

2.3.1. pH, pE and Conductivity

220 The pH and the conductivity of the soil were measured after shaking 5 grams of soil during 1 hour in
221 25 ml of water. The redox potential was determined after 30 minute shaking.

2.3.2. Determination of the Organic Matter

224 Organic matter content was estimated by means of the total organic carbon (TOC) according to the
225 classic method of Walkley-Black (Walkley and Black, 1934). This method involves the oxidation of the
226 soil organic matter with an excess of potassium dichromate (equation 1) and titration the excess with
227 Mohr's salt ($\text{Fe}(\text{NH}_4)_2(\text{SO}_4)_2$) (equation 2).

232 In this way, the amount of readily oxidizable organic matter (W_{ROOM}) is obtained. It is assumed that
233 organic matter contains 58% of C and that 77% of the organic matter is oxidized by this method. Thus,
234 a correction factor of 1.33 and 0.58 is applied to obtain the total amount of organic matter according to
235 the equation $\text{TOC}\% = (W_{\text{ROOM}} \cdot 1.33) / (m_{\text{soil}} \cdot 0.58)$, where W_{ROOM} is the amount of readily oxidizable
236 organic matter calculated by titration and m_{soil} is the amount of soil weighed for the titration.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Physicochemical parameters

241 All the values of some physicochemical properties were among normal ranges of typical clay soils.
1
2 242 The variable that changed the most among different soils was the conductivity. Soils from the left side
3
4 243 of the secondary road showed the higher values (200-250 $\mu\text{S}\cdot\text{cm}^{-1}$), whereas the lowest ones were
5
6 244 found in the soil samples from the right side of the same road (50-100 $\mu\text{S}\cdot\text{cm}^{-1}$). Soil samples from the
7
8 245 highway present conductivity values in the range 100-150 $\mu\text{S}\cdot\text{cm}^{-1}$. Conductivity is an indicator of the
9
10 246 soluble salts, therefore it seems that a different behaviour exists among soils from different locations.

11
12 247
13
14 248 The pH value was in the range 7.4-7.8 as is expected in clay soils with low carbonate presence and
15
16 249 the pE was around 200-250 mV indicating aerobic conditions. Soil samples were poor in organic
17
18 250 matter as is deduced from the percentage of the TOC values, less than 5% except in samples from
19
20 251 the left side in the secondary road where the amount of organic matter is a bit higher (4-7%). This left
21
22 252 side showed the highest conductivity values, maybe related to the ionic content of the organic matter.
23

24 253

26 254 **3.2. Chemometric analysis of the metal concentration**

27
28 255

29
30 256 In a first approach, roadside soils from the secondary road and the highway were screened in order to
31
32 257 establish TREs and the impacted areas. 50 of the 60 tested elements (Ag, As, B, Ba, Be, Bi, Cd, Ce,
33
34 258 Co, Cr, Cs, Cu, Dy, Er, Eu, Ga, Gd, Ge, Hf, Ho, In, K, La, Li, Lu, Mg, Mo, Na, Nb, Nd, Ni, Pb, Pr, Rb,
35
36 259 Sb, Se, Sm, Sn, Sr, Tb, Te, Th, Tl, Tm, U, V, Y, Yb, Zn, Zr) were determined above the detection limit
37
38 260 in the soil extracts. These results were statistically treated with "The Unscrambler 9.2" software. After
39
40 261 centring and autoscaling the data, principal component analysis (PCA) revealed two main components
41
42 262 accounting for 68% of the total variance (PC1, 51%; PC2, 17%). The projection of the scores and
43
44 263 loadings on the bi-dimensional space, defined by these two principal components, is shown in Fig. 1.
45
46 264 Samples can be grouped according to sampling point in three groups. Samples from the west (left)
47
48 265 roadside of the secondary road (SR L) clearly differentiate from the rest, and are gathered in the right
49
50 266 side of the x axis (PC1). Samples from the highway (H 0.5, H 3 and H 6) form another group in the
51
52 267 lower side of the graphic. Finally, samples from the east roadside (right) of the secondary road (SR R),
53
54 268 further samples from the highway (H 9) and control soils are together on the left side of the x-axis
55
56 269 (PC1).

57
58 270
59
60
61
62
63
64
65

271 When the scores and loading plots are overlapped, the concentrations of Cd, Cr, Cu, Hf, Mo, Nb, Ni,
1
2 272 Pb, Sb, Sn, Sr, Zn and Zr are clearly the variables that explain most of the variance of the SR L
3
4 273 sampling point. In fact, the concentration of these metals was considerably higher in these soil
5
6 274 samples as can be seen in Fig. 2, where average concentration of some of these metals has been
7
8 275 represented by sampling area: samples from the west and east roadside of the secondary road (SR L
9
10 276 and SR R), samples from the highway (HG) and control soils (C). The rest of the above mentioned
11
12 277 metals (data not shown) have the same behaviour. Therefore, soil samples are grouped according to
13
14 278 their TREs concentration in samples heavily impacted by the traffic (west roadside at the secondary
15
16 279 road, SR L), samples moderately impacted by the traffic (samples from the highway, H 0.5, H 3 and
17
18 280 H 6) and samples not impacted by the traffic (east roadside at the secondary road, further samples at
19
20 281 the highway and control soils, SR R, H 9 and C).

21
22 282
23
24 283 The high metal concentration in samples from the west roadside of the secondary road suggests an
25
26 284 accumulation of TREs for a long time since it is a very old road and has borne all the traffic of the area
27
28 285 in the past, a time were the exhausted fumes from cars were not under strict environmental control.
29
30 286 This can be seen also in the extremely high Pb concentration because of the use of leaded gasoline
31
32 287 for many years. Although the consumption of leaded gasoline in Spain has been banned since August
33
34 288 2001 (Law, 2001), a high Pb concentration in roadside still remains. It must be also beard in mind that
35
36 289 the dominant wind direction in this area is from NW and the existing road cut protect this roadside from
37
38 290 the wind and also from the rain. Therefore, there is not dispersion and exhaust fumes from vehicles
39
40 291 impact directly the soil and are not washed by the rain.

41
42 292
43
44 293 **3.3. Traffic-related elements profile on roadside soils**

45
46 294
47
48 295 After screening of the top soils and establishment of a first list of TREs, the horizontal and vertical
49
50 296 distribution of the TREs was investigated. To perform this study the west roadside soil of the old road
51
52 297 was excluded due to the high concentrations of the trapped TREs (near saturation) that probably mask
53
54 298 the vertical and horizontal trends. As it could be expected after the chemometric treatment of the metal
55
56 299 concentration data in soil samples from the secondary road and the highway, the different exposure
57
58 300 time to the traffic impact and, therefore, the age of the road, could appear to be an important factor to

301 take into account when investigating the accumulation of TREs in roadside soils. Thus, the study was
1
2 302 extended including the other two sampling sites from roundabouts at Berango and Sopelana with only
3
4 303 5 and 1 years old in service, respectively.

5
6 304
7
8 305 High concentrations of some metals were found in upper soils close to the highway (S0m and S1m)
9
10 306 compared with those values obtained in deeper soils and at 3 meters of horizontal distance to the
11
12 307 highway (S3m). Furthermore, concentrations show a severe decreasing profile with depth and
13
14 308 distance to the highway, reaching a constant value in the deepest samples. The fact that element
15
16 309 concentrations in depth reach a plateau and that it was similar to the concentration of soils at 3 meters
17
18 310 of distance, suggests that those values could correspond to the natural values of the elements in
19
20 311 these soils. Besides, these values are in agreement with those given by IHOBE, the Basque
21
22 312 Environmental Public Corporation, for some metals as background levels in The Basque Country soils
23
24 313 (Table 1).

25
26 314
27
28 315 Three different types of metal profiles were found in the roadside soil samples from the highway.
29
30 316 Some elements show a steep decreasing profile between upper and deeper soils. That is the case of
31
32 317 Ti, Cu, Zn, Mo, Cd, Sn, Sb, W, Hg, Nb and Pb, whereas others like Na, Mg, Ca, V, Cr, Mn, Co, Ni, Sr,
33
34 318 Ag or Ba have a less sharper profile. All of these elements have a traffic-related emission source
35
36 319 (Hjortenkrans et al., 2006; Wei and Yang, 2010) and most of these elements were already related to
37
38 320 traffic emissions in the preliminary screening but in this study other elements such as Na, Mg, Ca, Ti,
39
40 321 V, Mn, Co, Ag, Ba, W and Hg also appear. The last group of elements is formed by Li, K, Al, Fe, As,
41
42 322 Ti, and REE, and their concentrations in soil keep nearly constant, without a significant trend.
43
44 323 Therefore, there is a clear input of some of these elements from the road traffic to the roadside soil in
45
46 324 the highway. The effect of traffic on the soils is more important in those samples closest to the
47
48 325 highway. In fact, the metal concentrations in soils at 3 meters of distance to the highway were similar
49
50 326 to the background values, except in the upper 2 cm (S3m A), where values were slightly higher. Fig. 3
51
52 327 is a 3D representation of the concentration of the Zn metal, showing the above-mentioned decreasing
53
54 328 behaviour with depth and distance and the metal accumulation in topsoil. Other TREs, like Cd, Pb
55
56 329 and Mo, present the same behaviour, whereas Fe, Al, Dy and Y show the normal behaviour of soil
57
58 330 natural elements not affected by traffic emissions.

331

1
2 332 The same study was carried out in soils from the less impacted roads in Berango (BE) and Sopelana
3
4 333 (SO). These soils have been subjected to the traffic impact for a shorter time since they are new roads
5
6 334 and therefore the accumulation of metals is lower than in the highway. In fact, there is no trend with
7
8 335 the depth and the distance to the road as occurs in soils taken in the highway and the concentration of
9
10 336 the represented TREs keeps constant or without a clear trend. Furthermore, metal concentration
11
12 337 ranges at these both sites are quite lower than the concentrations found in the highway.

13
14 338
15
16 339 Finally, a chemometric analysis of the soil transects from the three different sampling sites was done.
17
18 340 The concentration of the 46 measured elements was included in the analysis. In Fig. 4 the bi-plot with
19
20 341 the scores and loadings of the obtained PCA is shown. The first two PCs account for the 80% of the
21
22 342 total variance (PC1 51%, PC2 29%). PC1 can be associated to REE concentration and therefore, to
23
24 343 the origin of the soil. On the other hand, PC2 is related with the depth of the soil samples. Topsoil
25
26 344 samples closest to the highway appear together in the upper-left side of the PCA, whereas deeper
27
28 345 ones are in the bottom together with further samples from the highway. Middle-depth samples are
29
30 346 found between topsoil and deep soils. This fact shows the existing metal gradient concentration in
31
32 347 soils close to the highway as has been previously shown. Moreover, metals having a gradient profile
33
34 348 can be ascertained as they appear together differentiating topsoil from deep soils. Soil samples from
35
36 349 Berango and Sopelana appear in the right side and there is no difference among samples from
37
38 350 different depth or distance to the road. They appear mixed between them and without any depth order,
39
40 351 unlike the samples from the highway.

41
42 352
43
44 353 **3.4. Assessment of the traffic impact on roadside soils**
45
46 354 The assessment of the traffic impact on the studied areas was carried out with the aim of ascertaining
47
48 355 the pollution state of soils from the different places. Geoaccumulation indexes were calculated using
49
50 356 the background values obtained from deeper soils, since metal concentrations reach a plateau and
51
52 357 these values agree with those given by IHOBE, the Baque Environmental Public Corporation, for
53
54 358 some metals listed in Table 1 as has been previously stated.

55
56 359

57
58
59
60
61
62
63
64
65

360 In the Fig. 5 the pollution state of all the soils analyzed in this work has been summarised.
1
2 361 Geoaccumulation indexes of the most important TREs has been represented: Cd, Cu, Ni, Pb, Sb, Sn
3
4 362 and Zn. The most impacted soils correspond to those in the west roadside of the secondary road (SR
5
6 363 L) and in the highway at 1 metre distance since these soils have the highest I_{geo} values. As can be
7
8 364 seen in the Fig. 5 roadside soils from the secondary road appear to be polluted ($I_{geo} > 1$) in Cd, Pb, Sb
9
10 365 and Zn, whereas those from the highway are polluted in Cd, Cu, Pb, Sb, Sn and Zn but also in Hg,
11
12 366 Mo, Nb, Ti and W (data not shown).

13
14 367
15
16 368 The worst case, as has been previously stated, is the high pollution of Pb ($I_{geo} > 4$) in soils from the
17
18 369 west roadside of the secondary road due to the past use of leaded gasoline. On the contrary, the east
19
20 370 roadside from the secondary road (SR R) and soil samples at 3 metre distance to the highway appear
21
22 371 to be non-polluted in all the studied elements, $I_{geo} < 1$. Soils from Berango and Sopelana appear to be
23
24 372 not polluted for most of the TREs ($I_{geo} < 1$). Only Sb has a I_{geo} value of 2 in samples from Sopelana
25
26 373 classifying them as slightly polluted soils. Other significant metal that presents certain pollution level
27
28 374 was Cd with a $I_{geo} = 2$ in topsoil at 1 metre distance from the road and values between 1-2 at 0 m (very
29
30 375 slightly polluted). These soils are also very slightly polluted in Cu ($1 > I_{geo} < 2$) both at 0 and 1 metre of
31
32 376 distance, and in the case of Berango, also in Pb. The rest of elements have values of
33
34 377 geoaccumulation index below 1.

35
36 378
37
38 379 The elevated concentration values of Sb must be highlighted. In particular, Sb is the only TRE found in
39
40 380 the Sopelana sampling site, a new road with very low traffic density but which is located in the
41
42 381 surroundings of the beach and during the summer, many cars park in the roadside. This is in
43
44 382 agreement with a recent work that studied the Sb speciation in different fractions of urban dust in
45
46 383 Buenos Aires, Argentina (Fujiwara et al., 2011), highlighting its presence as a TRE together with Cu
47
48 384 and Pb, like we have detected in these new soils. Besides, it is known that Sb is used in brake linings
49
50 385 (Hjortenkrans et al., 2007; Thorpe and Harrison, 2008) and could be released to roadside soils in the
51
52 386 dust originated by the brake wear when cars park in the roadside.

53
54 387
55
56 388 On the other hand, the Indicative Values for Assessment (VIE) are guideline values to establish the
57
58 389 risk acceptance limits for the different uses of a soil in the Basque Country. There are three levels of
59
60
61
62
63
64
65

390 acceptance. VIE-A is a reference level and below it, it is possible to state that the soil is not affected
1
2 391 and there is no risk for the human health. VIE-B marks the lower limit of acceptability of the risk.
3
4 392 Values lower than this but higher than VIE-A involve acceptable risk, whereas values higher than VIE-
5
6 393 B suggest an unacceptable risk and a more detailed study of the zone must be carried out. VIE-C
7
8 394 represents the upper limit of acceptability of the risk and when exceeded, implies a serious risk to the
9
10 395 ecosystem and soil recovery measurements are required.

11 396
12
13
14 397 The average concentration of metals in some of the sampling locations have been plotted in Fig. 6
15
16 398 against the VIE-B and VIE-C values. As can be seen, the concentration of some elements is higher
17
18 399 than the VIE-B, even the VIE-C, in roadside samples from the highway and from the west roadside of
19
20 400 the secondary road. In the case of roadside soils at 1 meter of distance to the highway, the
21
22 401 concentration of Mo, Cd, Ni, Cu and Pb is higher than the VIE-B value, whereas Hg and Zn exceed
23
24 402 the VIE-C value. The concentration of Cd, Cu and Zn in soils from the west roadside in the secondary
25
26 403 road was also above the VIE-B, whereas Pb concentration surpassed the VIE-C. Although Berango
27
28 404 and Sopelana do not have high values for most of the TREs, the concentration of Cu is above the VIE-
29
30 405 B in both sites and Pb and Zn levels are higher than VIE-B in Berango and Sopelana respectively.
31
32 406 There were no more limit cases in the rest of the sites. The concentration of As and Co, the other two
33
34 407 metals for which the Basque Government regulates its concentration in soil, are lower than the VIE-B
35
36 408 and do not suppose a risk for the environment in any of the studied areas.

37
38 409
39
40 410 Metals such as, Pb, Zn and Hg, have been measured recently at unexpected moderate concentrations
41
42 411 in the sediments of the Bilbao estuary after removing the industrial sources of pollution (Fdez-Ortiz de
43
44 412 Vallejuelo et al., 2010; Fernández et al., 2008) as well as in the Urdaibai estuary (Bartolome et al.,
45
46 413 2006) indicating that traffic could be the source for them (probably through a run-off process from soils
47
48 414 behind the roads circumvolving both estuaries).

49
50 415

416 **4. Conclusions**

51
52 417
53
54
55 418 This work showed the traffic impact that happens in roadside soils from roads with a high traffic
56
57 419 density, leading to a high traffic-related element concentration in them. ICP-MS semi-quantitative
58
59
60
61
62
63
64
65

420 analysis of the acid extracted soils allows the fast determination of most soil elements as a first tool for
1
2 421 evaluating the candidate sites to suffer the traffic impact. The studied area could be easily fenced in
3
4 422 the most impacted sampling points after a first screening of the concentration of 60 elements in soils.
5
6 423 Cd, Cr, Cu, Hf, Mo, Nb, Ni, Pb, Sb, Sn, Sr, Zn and Zr were identified as traffic-related elements (TREs)
7
8 424 after chemometric treatment of the obtained results. The concentration of these metals in the west
9
10 425 roadside of the old secondary road studied appears at higher concentrations than the rest of sampling
11
12 426 areas, including the control soils. This high metal concentration values in that secondary road can be
13
14 427 explained due to a long-term accumulation of metals from the past decades.
15

16 428
17
18 429 The quantitative analysis of the vertical and horizontal profile of concentration of metals reveals that
19
20 430 there is an accumulation of TREs on topsoil of roadsides affected by high traffic impact during long
21
22 431 time. For this reason, a high decreasing profile with depth and distance to the road/highway in the
23
24 432 concentration of the above mentioned elements was detected in roadside soils from the studied
25
26 433 highway (more than 15 years in service), but not in the roundabouts from Berango and Sopelana (less
27
28 434 than 5 years in service). Here, the concentration of TREs keeps constant with depth and distance to
29
30 435 the road since they are new roads and they have not been exposed to the traffic impact enough time
31
32 436 to accumulate the metals in topsoil.
33

34 437
35
36 438 The use of the geoaccumulation index to assess the impact and the contamination degree of the
37
38 439 roadside soils concluded that the secondary road and the highway are much more polluted by the
39
40 440 traffic emissions than the other studied roads. Pollution of the soil decreases rapidly with distance to
41
42 441 the highway and soils are classified as non-polluted at 3 meters of distance. In the newer roads the
43
44 442 geoaccumulation indexes suggest that a slight pollution of Sb, Cd, Pb and Cu, has started in a site
45
46 443 with less than 5 years at service. In particular, Sb seems to be the most important TRE impacting the
47
48 444 soil. Regarding the indicative values for assessment (VIE) that the Basque Environmental Public
49
50 445 Corporation (IHOBE) sets up for some toxic metal concentration in soils, some of them were detected
51
52 446 above the values established for the acceptability of the risk. In the case of the concentration of Pb in
53
54 447 roadside soils from the secondary road, and Hg and Zn in the highway, the upper limit of acceptability
55
56 448 of the risk (VIE-C) is surpassed.
57

58 449
59
60
61
62
63
64
65

450 To sum up, the obtained results illustrate the accumulation of metals that occurs in roadside soils due
1
2 451 to the traffic emissions. This accumulation is higher in roads with more years in service and more
3
4 452 traffic density, reaching in some cases metal concentrations on topsoil above the target values
5
6 453 regulated by the local administration. The use of the geoaccumulation indexes is a good approach to
7
8 454 establish the range and pollution degree of soils impacted by the traffic emissions. Although leaded
9
10 455 petrol was banned more than ten years ago, Pb continues being a problem for the environment as
11
12 456 high concentrations still remains in roadside soils. Apart from this well-known TRE other metals, such
13
14 457 as Sb, are starting to accumulate in newer roads as a result of its presence in nowadays brakes.
15
16 458 Further actions should be adopted to avoid spreading the pollution from topsoil near the roads to other
17
18 459 areas since elevated concentrations of some TREs are being detected in the sediments of the Bilbao
19
20 460 estuary as a consequence of, probably, the metal run-off originated by the rain.
21

22 461

24 462 **Acknowledgments**

25
26 463 This work has been financially supported by the SUDOE Interreg IV B programme through the
27
28 464 ORQUE SUDOE (Ref. SOE3/P2/F591/5) project. J.A. Carrero is grateful to the University of the
29
30 465 Basque Country (UPV-EHU) for his post-doctoral fellowship.
31

32 466

References

- 1
2
3
4
5
6
7
8
9
10
11
12
13
14
15
16
17
18
19
20
21
22
23
24
25
26
27
28
29
30
31
32
33
34
35
36
37
38
39
40
41
42
43
44
45
46
47
48
49
50
51
52
53
54
55
56
57
58
59
60
61
62
63
64
65
- 2
3 Aatmeeyata, Sharma M. Polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons, elemental and organic carbon emissions from tire-wear. *Sci. Total Environ.* 2011; 408: 4563-4568.
- 5
6 Adachi K, Tainosho Y. Characterization of heavy metal particles embedded in tire dust. *Environ. Int.* 2004; 30: 1009-1017.
- 7
8 Amato F, Pandolfi M, Moreno T, Furger M, Pey J, Alastuey A, et al. Sources and variability of inhalable road dust particles in three European cities. *Atmos. Environ.* 2011; 45: 6777-6787.
- 9
10 Apeageyi E, Bank MS, Spengler JD. Distribution of heavy metals in road dust along an urban-rural gradient in Massachusetts. *Atmos. Environ.* 2011; 45: 2310-2323.
- 11
12 Bartolome L, Tueros I, Cortazar E, Raposo JC, Sanz J, Zuloaga O, et al. Distribution of trace organic contaminants and total mercury in sediments from the Bilbao and Urdaibai Estuaries (Bay of Biscay). *Mar. Pollut. Bull.* 2006; 52: 1111-1117.
- 14
15 Bergbaeck B, Johansson K, Mohlander U. Urban metal flows - a case study of Stockholm. *Water, Air, Soil Pollut.: Focus* 2001; 1: 3-24.
- 16
17 BFA/DFB Evaluación del tráfico de las carreteras de Vizcaya 2004
- 17
18 Bretzel F, Calderisi M. Metal Contamination in Urban Soils of Coastal Tuscany (Italy). *Environ. Monit. Assess.* 2006; 118: 319-335.
- 19
20 Carrero JA, Goienaga N, Fdez-Ortiz de Vallejuelo S, Arana G, Madariaga JM. Classification of archaeological pieces into their respective stratum by a chemometric model based on the soil concentration of 25 selected elements. *Spectrochim. Acta, Part B* 2010; 65: 279-286.
- 22
23 Councell TB, Duckenfield KU, Landa ER, Callender E. Tire-Wear Particles as a Source of Zinc to the Environment. *Environ. Sci. Technol.* 2004; 38: 4206-4214.
- 24
25 Chen X, Xia X, Zhao Y, Zhang P. Heavy metal concentrations in roadside soils and correlation with urban traffic in Beijing, China. *J. Hazard. Mater.* 2010; 181: 640-646.
- 26
27 de Miguel E, Llamas JF, Chacon E, Berg T, Larssen S, Royset O, et al. Origin and patterns of distribution of trace elements in street dust: unleaded petrol and urban lead. *Atmos. Environ.* 1997; 31: 2733-2740.
- 29
30 Directive 98/70/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 13 October 1998 relating to the quality of petrol and diesel fuels and amending Council Directive 93/12/EEC. <http://eur-lex.europa.eu/en/index.htm> Retrieved at 09.01.2013
- 32
33 Dongarra G, Manno E, Varrica D. Possible markers of traffic-related emissions. *Environ. Monit. Assess.* 2009; 154: 117-125.
- 34
35 EPA Method 3051A. Microwave assisted acid digestion of sediments, sludges, soils and oils
- 35
36 Fdez-Ortiz de Vallejuelo S, Arana G, de Diego A, Madariaga JM. Risk assessment of trace elements in sediments: The case of the estuary of the Nerbion-Ibaizabal River (Basque Country). *J. Hazard. Mater.* 2010; 181: 565-573.
- 37
38 Fernández S, Villanueva U, de Diego A, Arana G, Madariaga JM. Monitoring trace elements (Al, As, Cr, Cu, Fe, Mn, Ni and Zn) in deep and surface waters of the estuary of the Nerbioi-Ibaizabal River (Bay of Biscay, Basque Country). *J. Marine Syst.* 2008; 72: 332-341.

- 1 Fujiwara F, Rebagliati RJ, Marrero J, Gómez D, Smichowski P. Antimony as a traffic-related element
2 in size-fractionated road dust samples collected in Buenos Aires. *Microchem. J.* 2011; 97: 62-67.
- 3 Garcia R, Millán E. Assessment of Cd, Pb and Zn contamination in roadside soils and grasses from
4 Gipuzkoa (Spain). *Chemosphere* 1998; 37: 1615-1625.
- 5 Gratani L, Taglioni S, Crescente MF. The accumulation of lead in agricultural soil and vegetation along
6 a highway. *Chemosphere* 1992; 24: 941-9.
- 7 Hjortenkrans D, Bergbäck B, Häggerud A. New Metal Emission Patterns in Road Traffic Environments.
8 *Environ. Monit. Assess.* 2006; 117: 85-98.
- 9 Hjortenkrans D, Bergbäck B, Häggerud A. Metal Emissions from Brake Linings and Tires: Case
10 Studies of Stockholm, Sweden 1995/1998 and 2005. *Environ. Sci. Technol.* 2007; 41: 5224-5230.
- 11 IHOBE. Calidad del Suelo. Valores Indicativos de Evaluación (VIE-A, VIE-B, VIE-C). Departamento de
12 Ordenación del Territorio, Vivienda y Medio Ambiente. Gobierno Vasco, Vitoria-Gazteiz, 1998, pp.
13 272.
- 14 Johansson C, Norman M, Burman L. Road traffic emission factors for heavy metals. *Atmos. Environ.*
15 2009; 43: 4681-4688.
- 16 Laborda F, Medrano J, Castillo JR. Quality of quantitative and semiquantitative results in inductively
17 coupled plasma mass spectrometry. *J. Anal. At. Spectrom.* 2001; 16: 732-738.
- 18 Lagerwerff JV, Specht AW. Contamination of roadside soil and vegetation with cadmium, nickel, lead,
19 and zinc. *Environ. Sci. Technol.* 1970; 4: 583-586.
- 20 Law RD 785/2001. <http://www.boe.es/boe/dias/2001/07/07/pdfs/A24775-24776.pdf> Retrieved at
21 09.01.2013
- 22 Li F-R, Kang L-F, Gao X-Q, Hua W, Yang F-W, Hei W-L. Traffic-Related Heavy Metal Accumulation in
23 Soils and Plants in Northwest China. *Soil and Sediment Contamination: An International Journal*
24 2007; 16: 473 - 484.
- 25 Li H-b, Yu S, Li G-l, Deng H, Luo X-s. Contamination and source differentiation of Pb in park soils
26 along an urban-rural gradient in Shanghai. *Environ. Pollut.* 2011; 159: 3536-3544.
- 27 Liu H, Chen L-P, Ai Y-W, Yang X, Yu Y-H, Zuo Y-B, et al. Heavy metal contamination in soil alongside
28 mountain railway in Sichuan, China. *Environ. Monit. Assess.* 2009; 152: 25-33.
- 29 Lough GC, Schauer JJ, Park J-S, Shafer MM, DeMinter JT, Weinstein JP. Emissions of Metals
30 Associated with Motor Vehicle Roadways. *Environ. Sci. Technol.* 2005; 39: 826-836.
- 31 MacKinnon G, MacKenzie AB, Cook GT, Pulford ID, Duncan HJ, Scott EM. Spatial and temporal
32 variations in Pb concentrations and isotopic composition in road dust, farmland soil and vegetation
33 in proximity to roads since cessation of use of leaded petrol in the UK. *Sci. Total Environ.* 2011;
34 409: 5010-5019.
- 35 Massadeh AM, Jaradat QM, Momani KA, Saleem MA. Distribution of Heavy Metals in Some Tree
36 Leaves along the Main Road in an Agricultural Area. *Communications in Soil Science and Plant*
37 *Analysis* 2009; 40: 1254 - 1267.
- 38 McKenzie ER, Money JE, Green PG, Young TM. Metals associated with stormwater-relevant brake
39 and tire samples. *Sci. Total Environ.* 2009; 407: 5855-5860.
- 40 Meland S, Borgstrøm R, Heier LS, Rosseland BO, Lindholm O, Salbu B. Chemical and ecological
41 effects of contaminated tunnel wash water runoff to a small Norwegian stream. *Sci. Total Environ.*
42 2010; 408: 4107-4117.

1 Müller G. Index of geoaccumulation in sediments of the Rhine River. *Geojournal* 1969; 2: 108-118.

2 2 Oliva SR, Espinosa AJF. Monitoring of heavy metals in topsoils, atmospheric particles and plant
3 3 leaves to identify possible contamination sources. *Microchem. J.* 2007; 86: 131-139.

4 4 Olowoyo JO, van Heerden E, Fischer JL, Baker C. Trace metals in soil and leaves of *Jacaranda*
5 5 *mimosifolia* in Tshwane area, South Africa. *Atmos. Environ.* 2010; 44: 1826-1830.

6 6 Soldevila J, El Himri M, Pastor A, de la Guardia M. Evaluation of operational parameters affecting
7 7 semiquantitative multi-elemental analysis by inductively coupled plasma mass spectrometry. *J.*
8 8 *Anal. At. Spectrom.* 1998; 13: 803-807.

9 9 Sutherland RA, Tolosa CA, Tack FMG, Verloo MG. Characterization of selected element
10 10 concentrations and enrichment ratios in background and anthropogenically impacted roadside
11 11 areas. *Arch. Environ. Contam. Toxicol.* 2000; 38: 428-438.

12 12 Thorpe A, Harrison RM. Sources and properties of non-exhaust particulate matter from road traffic: A
13 13 review. *Sci. Total Environ.* 2008; 400: 270-282.

14 14 Veschambre S, Amouroux D, Moldovan M, Etchelecou A, Asta J, Donard OFX. Determination of
15 15 metallic pollutants in atmospheric particles, wet deposition and epiphytic lichens in the Pyrenees
16 16 mountains (Aspe Valley). *Journal de Physique IV: Proceedings* 2003; 107: 1341-1344.

17 17 Viard B, Pihan F, Promeyrat S, Pihan J-C. Integrated assessment of heavy metal (Pb, Zn, Cd)
18 18 highway pollution: bioaccumulation in soil, Graminaceae and land snails. *Chemosphere* 2004; 55:
19 19 1349-1359.

20 20 Walkley A, Black IA. An examination of Degtjareff method for determining soil organic matter and a
21 21 proposed modification of the chromic acid titration method. *Soil Sci.* 1934; 37: 29-37.

22 22 Wei B, Yang L. A review of heavy metal contaminations in urban soils, urban road dusts and
23 23 agricultural soils from China. *Microchem. J.* 2010; 94: 99-107.

24 24 Wiseman CLS, Zereini F, Püttmann W. Traffic-related trace element fate and uptake by plants
25 25 cultivated in roadside soils in Toronto, Canada. *Sci. Total Environ.* 2013; 442: 86-95.

26 26 Wu Y, Luo Y, Zou D, Ni J, Liu W, Teng Y, et al. Bioremediation of polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons
27 27 contaminated soil with *Monilinia* sp.: degradation and microbial community analysis.
28 28 *Biodegradation* 2008; 19: 247-257.

29 29

30 30

- 1
- 2
- 3
- 4
- 5
- 6
- 7
- 8
- 9
- 10
- 11
- 12
- 13
- 14
- 15
- 16
- 17
- 18
- 19
- 20
- 21
- 22
- 23
- 24
- 25
- 26
- 27
- 28
- 29
- 30
- 31
- 32
- 33
- 34
- 35
- 36
- 37
- 38
- 39
- 40
- 41
- 42
- 43
- 44
- 45
- 46
- 47
- 48
- 49
- 50
- 51
- 52
- 53
- 54
- 55
- 56
- 57
- 58
- 59
- 60
- 61
- 62
- 63
- 64
- 65

Tables

Table 1. Background levels of some metals (mg/Kg) in soils from the Basque Country (IHOBE, 1998).

	Cd	Cr	Cu	Ni	Pb	Zn
This study	0.1	38	15	21	22	60
IHOBE	0.2	30	14	19	22	65

Figure captions

Fig. S1. Pictures of the sampling sites: a) the secondary road; b) the highway; c) the roundabout from Berango; and d) the roundabout from Sopelana.

Fig. 1. Scores and loadings plot for the first two PCs resulting from the PCA of all elements determined in roadside soils from the secondary road and the highway. C: control; SR L: west roadside of the secondary road; SR R: east roadside of the secondary road; H 0.5, H 3, H 6 and H 9: highway soil samples at 0.5, 3, 6 and 9 m distance from highway.

Fig. 2. Average value of some metal concentration in SR L and SR R: west and east roadside of the secondary road; HG: highway; and C: control.

Fig. 3. 3D representation of the variation of Zn concentration (mg/Kg) with the depth and distance to the highway in roadside soil samples from the highway.

Fig. 4. PCA of the soil transects from the 3 different sampling sites at the highway, Berango and Sopelana.

Fig. 5. Geoaccumulation indexes for some TREs in the different studied areas.

Fig. 6. Concentration of some metals and their regulated values for the Basque Country, given by IHOBE (Basque Environmental Public Corporation).

Fig 1 ByN.tif
[Click here to download high resolution image](#)

Fig 2 ByN.tif
[Click here to download high resolution image](#)

Fig 3 ByN.tif
[Click here to download high resolution image](#)

Fig 5 ByN.tif
[Click here to download high resolution image](#)

Fig S1 ByN.tif

[Click here to download Supplementary Material: Fig S1 ByN.tif](#)

Fig 1.tif

[Click here to download Supplementary Material: Fig 1.tif](#)

Fig 2.tif

[Click here to download Supplementary Material: Fig 2.tif](#)

Fig 3.tif

[Click here to download Supplementary Material: Fig 3.tif](#)

Fig 4.tif

[Click here to download Supplementary Material: Fig 4.tif](#)

Fig 5.tif

[Click here to download Supplementary Material: Fig 5.tif](#)

Fig.6.tif

[Click here to download Supplementary Material: Fig.6.tif](#)

Supplementary Tables.doc

[Click here to download Supplementary Material: Supplementary Tables.doc](#)